

Some new classes of neutrosophic minimal open sets

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Abstract: This article focuses on N_m - β -open, β -interior and β -closure operators using neutrosophic minimal structures. We investigate properties of such concepts and we introduced the concepts of N_m - β -continuous, N_m - β -closed graph, N_m - β -compact and almost N_m - β -compact. Finally, we introduced the concepts of N_m -regular-open sets and N_m - π -open sets and investigate some properties.

Key words: N_m - β -continuous, N_m - β -closed graph, N_m - β -compact, almost N_m - β -compact, N_m -regular-open and N_m - π -open

1. Introduction

Zadeh's [17] Fuzzy set laid the foundation of many fields such as intuitionistic fuzzy, neutrosophic set, rough sets. Later, researchers developed K. T. Atanassov's [4] intuitionistic fuzzy set theory in many fields such as differential equations, topology, computerscience and so on. F. Smarandache [15, 16] found that some objects have indeterminacy or neutral other than membership and non-membership. So he coined the notion of neutrosophy. V. Popa & T. Noiri [12] introduced the notions of minimal structure which is a generalization of a topology on a given nonempty set. We introduced the concepts of \mathcal{M} -continuous maps. M. Karthika et al [11] studied neutrosophic minimal structure spaces. S. Ganesan and F. Smarandache [9] studied N_m -semi-open in neutrosophic minimal structure spaces. S. Ganesan et al [10] studied N_m -pre-continuous maps. This article focuses on N_m - β -open, β -interior and β -closure operators using neutrosophic minimal structures. We investigate properties of such concepts and we introduced the notions of N_m - β -continuous, N_m - β -closed graph, N_m - β -compact and almost N_m - β -compact and investigate some properties for such concepts. Finally, we introduced N_m -regular-open, N_m - π -open sets and investigate fundamental properties.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [15, 16] Neutrosophic set (in short ns) K on a set $G \neq \emptyset$ is defined by $K = \{ \prec a, P_K(a), Q_K(a), R_K(a) \succ : a \in G \}$, where $P_K : G \rightarrow [0,1]$, $Q_K : G \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $R_K : G \rightarrow [0,1]$ denotes the membership of an object, indeterminacy and non-membership of an object, for each a on G to K , respectively and $0 \leq P_K(a) + Q_K(a) + R_K(a) \leq 3$ for each $a \in G$.

Proposition 2.1. [13] For any ns S , then the following conditions are holds:

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1. $0_{\sim} \leq S, 0_{\sim} \leq 0_{\sim}$.
2. $S \leq 1_{\sim}, 1_{\sim} \leq 1_{\sim}$.

Definition 2.2. [13] Let $K = \{ \prec a, P_K(a), Q_K(a), R_K(a) \succ : a \in G \}$ be a ns.

1. A ns K is an empty set i.e., $K = 0_{\sim}$ if 0 is membership of an object and 0 is an indeterminacy and 1 is a non-membership of an object respectively. i.e., $0_{\sim} = \{g, (0, 0, 1) : g \in G\}$
2. A ns K is a universal set i.e., $K = 1_{\sim}$ if 1 is membership of an object and 1 is an indeterminacy and 0 is a non-membership of an object respectively. $1_{\sim} = \{g, (1, 1, 0) : g \in G\}$
3. $K_1 \cup K_2 = \{a, \max \{P_{K_1}(a), P_{K_2}(a)\}, \max \{Q_{K_1}(a), Q_{K_2}(a)\}, \min \{R_{K_1}(a), R_{K_2}(a)\} : a \in G\}$
4. $K_1 \cap K_2 = \{a, \min \{P_{K_1}(a), P_{K_2}(a)\}, \min \{Q_{K_1}(a), Q_{K_2}(a)\}, \max \{R_{K_1}(a), R_{K_2}(a)\} : a \in G\}$
5. $K_1^C = \{ \prec a, R_K(a), 1 - Q_K(a), P = P_K(a) \succ : a \in G \}$

Definition 2.3. [13] Neutrosophic topology (nt) in Salama's sense on a nonempty set G is a family τ of ns in G satisfying three conditions:

1. Empty set (0_{\sim}) and universal set (1_{\sim}) are members of τ .
2. $K_1 \cap K_2 \in \tau$ where $K_1, K_2 \in \tau$.
3. $\cup K_{\delta} \in \tau$ for every $\{K_{\delta} : \delta \in \Delta\} \leq \tau$.

Definition 2.4. [11] The neutrosophic minimal structure space over a universal set G be denoted by N_m . N_m is said to be neutrosophic minimal structure space (in short, nms) over G if it satisfying following the axiom: $0_{\sim}, 1_{\sim} \in N_m$. A family of neutrosophic minimal structure space is denoted by (G, N_mG) .

Note that neutrosophic empty set and neutrosophic universal set can form a topology and it is known as neutrosophic minimal structure space.

Remark 2.1. [11] Each ns in nms is neutrosophic minimal open set (in short, nmo).
Complement of nmo is neutrosophic minimal closed set (in short, nmc).

Definition 2.5. [11] A is N_m -closed if and only if $N_m \text{cl}(A) = A$. Similarly, A is a N_m -open if and only if $N_m \text{int}(A) = A$.

Definition 2.6. [11] Let N_m be any nms and A be any neutrosophic set. Then

1. Every $A \in N_m$ is open and its complement is N_m closed.
2. N_m -closure of $A = \min \{F : F \text{ is a nmc and } F \geq A\}$ and it is denoted by $N_m \text{cl}(A)$.
3. N_m -interior of $A = \max \{F : F \text{ is a nmo and } F \leq A\}$ and it is denoted by $N_m \text{int}(A)$.

In general $N_m \text{int}(A)$ is subset of A and A is a subset of $N_m \text{cl}(A)$.

Proposition 2.2. [11] Let R and S are any ns of nms N_m over G . Then

1. $N_m^C = \{0, 1, R_i^C\}$ where R_i^C is a complement of ns R_i .

2. $G - N_m \text{int}(S) = N_m \text{cl}(G - S)$.
3. $G - N_m \text{cl}(S) = N_m \text{int}(G - S)$.
4. $N_m \text{cl}(R^C) = (N_m \text{cl}(R))^C = N_m \text{int}(R)$.
5. N_m closure of an empty set is an empty set and N_m closure of a universal set is a universal set. Similarly, N_m interior of an empty set and universal set respectively an empty and a universal set.
6. If S is a subset of R then $N_m \text{cl}(S) \leq N_m \text{cl}(R)$ and $N_m \text{int}(S) \leq N_m \text{int}(R)$.
7. $N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{cl}(R)) = N_m \text{cl}(R)$ and $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{int}(R)) = N_m \text{int}(R)$.
8. $N_m \text{cl}(R \vee S) = N_m \text{cl}(R) \vee N_m \text{cl}(S)$.
9. $N_m \text{cl}(R \wedge S) = N_m \text{cl}(R) \wedge N_m \text{cl}(S)$.

Definition 2.7. Let (G, N_{mG}) be a nms and $S \leq G$ is said to be

1. N_m -semi-open set (in short, N_m -so) [9] if $S \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(S))$.
 2. N_m -pre-open set (in short, N_m -po) [10] if $S \leq N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(S))$.
- The complement of above N_m -open set is called an N_m -closed set.

Definition 2.8. [11] Let (G, N_{mG}) be nms.

1. Arbitrary union of nmo in (G, N_{mG}) is nmo. (Union Property).
2. Finite intersection of nmo in (G, N_{mG}) is nmo. (intersection Property).

Definition 2.9. [11] A function $f: (G, N_{mG}) \rightarrow (H, N_{mH})$ is called neutrosophic minimal continuous map iff $f^{-1}(V) \in N_{mG}$ whenever $V \in N_{mH}$.

Definition 2.10. [11] let A be a ns in nms (G, N_{mG}) . Then Y is said to be neutrosophic minimal subspace if $(H, N_{mH}) = \{A \cap U : U \in N_{mH}\}$.

3. N_m - β -open sets

Definition 3.1. (G, N_{mG}) be a nms & $S \leq G$ is said to be N_m - β -open set (in short, N_m - β o) if $S \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(S)))$.

The complement of an N_m - β o is called an N_m - β -closed set(in short, N_m - β c)

Remark 3.1. (G, \mathcal{T}) be a nt & $S \leq G$ is said to be \mathcal{N} - β -open set [3] if $S \leq \mathcal{N} \text{cl}(\mathcal{N} \text{int}(\mathcal{N} \text{cl}(S)))$. If the nms N_{mG} is a topology, clearly an N_m - β o is \mathcal{N} - β -open.

Above definition of 3.1, trivially the following statement are obtained.

Lemma 3.1. Consider (G, N_{mG}) be a nms.

1. Every N_m -open is N_m - β o.
2. S is an N_m - β o iff $S \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(S)))$.

3. Every N_m -closed set is N_m - β -closed.
4. S is an N_m - β -closed set iff $N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(N_m \text{ int}(S))) \leq S$.

Theorem 3.1. (G, N_{mG}) be a nms. Any union of N_m - β o is N_m - β o.

Proof. Suppose A_δ be an N_m - β o for $\delta \in \Delta$. Above definition 3.1 and Proposition 2.2(6), $A_\delta \leq N_m \text{ cl}(N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(A_\delta))) \leq N_m \text{ cl}(N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(\bigcup A_\delta)))$. This implies $\bigcup A_\delta \leq N_m \text{ cl}(N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(\bigcup A_\delta)))$. Hence $\bigcup A_\delta$ is an N_m - β o. \square

Remark 3.2. Consider (G, N_{mG}) be a nms. Intersection of any 2 N_m - β o may not be N_m - β o.

Example 3.1. Consider $G = \{a\}$ with $N_m = \{0_\sim, P, Q, R, S, 1_\sim\}$ and $N_m^C = \{1_\sim, I, J, K, L, 0_\sim\}$ where $P = \prec (0.5, 0.6, 0.6) \succ$; $Q = \prec (0.4, 0.6, 0.8) \succ$; $R = \prec (0.4, 0.7, 0.9) \succ$; $S = \prec (0.5, 0.7, 0.6) \succ$; $I = \prec (0.6, 0.4, 0.5) \succ$; $J = \prec (0.8, 0.4, 0.4) \succ$; $K = \prec (0.9, 0.3, 0.4) \succ$; $L = \prec (0.6, 0.3, 0.5) \succ$

We know that $0_\sim = \{\prec g, 0, 0, 1 \succ : g \in G\}$, $1_\sim = \{\prec g, 1, 1, 0 \succ : g \in G\}$ and $0_\sim^C = \{\prec g, 1, 1, 0 \succ : g \in G\}$, $1_\sim^C = \{\prec g, 0, 0, 1 \succ : g \in G\}$.

Now we define the two N_m - β os as follows:

$A = \prec (0.6, 0.7, 0.9) \succ$; $B = \prec (0.5, 0.8, 0.4) \succ$

Here $N_m \text{ cl}(A) = 0_\sim^C$, $N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(A)) = 1_\sim$, $N_m \text{ cl}(N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(A))) = 0_\sim^C$ and

$N_m \text{ cl}(B) = 0_\sim^C$, $N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(B)) = 1_\sim$, $N_m \text{ cl}(N_m \text{ int}(N_m \text{ cl}(A))) = 0_\sim^C$. But $A \wedge B = \prec (0.5, 0.7, 0.9) \succ$ is not a N_m - β o in G .

Proposition 3.1. Let (G, N_{mG}) be a nms.

1. If S is a N_m so then it is a N_m - β o.
2. If S is a N_m -po then it is a N_m - β o.

Proof. (1) The proof is straightforward from the definitions.

(2) The proof is straightforward from the definitions. \square

Definition 3.2. Let (G, N_{mG}) be a nms.

1. N_m - β -closure of $A = \min \{S : S \text{ is } N_m\text{-}\beta\text{-closed set and } S \geq A\}$ and it is denoted by $N_m\text{-}\beta\text{cl}(A)$.
2. N_m - β -interior of $A = \max \{V : V \text{ is } N_m\text{-}\beta\text{ o and } V \leq A\}$ and it is denoted by $N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(A)$.

Theorem 3.2. Suppose (G, N_{mG}) be a nms and $R, S \leq G$. Then

1. $N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(0_\sim) = 0_\sim$.
2. $N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(1_\sim) = 1_\sim$.
3. $N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(R) \leq R$.
4. If $R \leq S$, then $N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(R) \leq N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(S)$.

5. R is N_m - β o iff N_m - β int(R) = R .
6. N_m - β int(N_m - β int(R)) = N_m - β int(R).
7. N_m - β cl ($G - R$) = $G - N_m$ - β int(R).

Proof. (1), (2) are Obvious.

(3), (4) are Obvious.

(5) It follows from Theorem 3.1.

(6) It follows condition from (5).

(7) For $R \leq G$, $G - N_m$ - β int(R) = $G - \max \{U : U \leq R, U \text{ is } N_m$ - β o\} = $\min \{G - U : U \leq R, U \text{ is } N_m$ - β o\} = $\min \{G - U : G - R \leq G - U\}$, $U \text{ is } N_m$ - β o\} = N_m - β cl ($G - R$). \square

Theorem 3.3. Let (G, N_mG) be a nms and $R, S \leq G$. Then

1. N_m - β cl (0_\sim) = 0_\sim .
2. N_m - β cl (1_\sim) = 1_\sim .
3. $R \leq N_m$ - β cl (R).
4. If $R \leq S$, then N_m - β cl (R) \leq N_m - β cl (S).
5. R is N_m - β c iff N_m - β cl (R) = R .
6. N_m - β cl (N_m - β cl (R)) = N_m - β cl (R).
7. N_m - β int($G - R$) = $G - N_m$ - β cl (R).

Proof. It is similar to the proof of above Theorem 3.2. \square

Theorem 3.4. Let (G, N_mG) be a nms and $S \leq G$. Then

1. $g \in N_m$ - β cl (S) iff $S \cap V \neq \emptyset$ for every N_m - β o V containing g .
2. $g \in N_m$ - β int(S) iff there exists an N_m - β o U such that $U \leq S$.

Proof. (1) Suppose there is an N_m - β o V containing g such that $S \cap V = \emptyset$. Then $G - V$ is an N_m - β c such that $S \leq G - V$, $g \notin G - V$. This implies $g \notin N_m$ - β cl (S).

The reverse relation is obvious.

(2) Obvious. \square

Lemma 3.2. Let (G, N_mG) be a nms and $S \leq G$. Then

1. N_m int(N_m cl(N_m int(S))) \leq N_m int(N_m cl(N_m int(N_m - β int(S)))) \leq N_m - β int(S).
2. N_m - β cl (S) \leq N_m cl(N_m int(N_m cl(N_m - β cl(S)))) \leq N_m cl(N_m int(N_m cl(S))).

Proof. (1) For $S \leq G$, by Theorem 3.3, N_m - β cl (S) is an N_m - β c set. Hence from Lemma 3.1, we have N_m int(N_m cl(N_m int(S))) \leq N_m int(N_m cl(N_m int(N_m - β int(S)))) \leq N_m - β int(S).

(2) It is similar to the proof of (1). \square

4. N_m - β -continuous map

Definition 4.1. Map $f : (G, N_{mG}) \rightarrow (H, N_{mH})$ is said to be N_m - β -continuous if $f^{-1}(O)$ is a N_m - β o in G , for each N_m -open O in H .

Theorem 4.1. *Every neutrosophic minimal continuous is N_m - β -continuous but not conversely.*

2. *Every N_m -semi-continuous is N_m - β -continuous but not conversely.*
3. *Every N_m -pre-continuous is N_m - β -continuous but not conversely.*

Proof. (1) The proof follows from [Lemma 3.1 (1)].

(2) The proof follows from [Proposition 3.1 (1)].

(3) The proof follows from [Proposition 3.1 (2)]. □

Theorem 4.2. *Map $f : G \rightarrow H$ be a function on 2 nms (G, N_{mG}) and (H, N_{mH}) . Then the following statements are equivalent:*

1. *f is N_m - β -continuous.*
2. *$f^{-1}(O)$ is an N_m - β o, for each N_m -open set O in H .*
3. *$f^{-1}(S)$ is an N_m - β c set, for each N_m -closed S in H .*
4. *$f(N_m\text{-}\beta\text{cl}(R)) \leq N_m\text{cl}(f(R))$, for $R \leq G$.*
5. *$N_m\text{-}\beta\text{cl}(f^{-1}(S)) \leq f^{-1}(N_m\text{cl}(S))$, for $S \leq H$.*
6. *$f^{-1}(N_m\text{int}(S)) \leq N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(f^{-1}(S))$, for $S \leq H$.*

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let O be an N_m -open in H and $g \in f^{-1}(O)$. By hypothesis, there exists an N_m - β o U_g containing g such that $f(U_g) \leq O$. This implies $g \in U_g \leq f^{-1}(O)$ for all $g \in f^{-1}(O)$. Hence by Theorem 3.1, $f^{-1}(O)$ is N_m - β o.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Obvious.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) For $R \leq G$, $f^{-1}(N_m\text{cl}(f(R))) = f^{-1}(\min \{F \leq H : f(R) \leq F \text{ and } F \text{ is } N_m\text{-closed}\}) = \min \{f^{-1}(F) \leq G : R \leq f^{-1}(F) \text{ and } F \text{ is } N_m\text{-}\beta\text{c}\} \geq \min \{K \leq G : R \leq K \text{ and } K \text{ is } N_m\text{-}\beta\text{c}\} = N_m\text{-}\beta\text{cl}(R)$. Hence $f(N_m\text{-}\beta\text{cl}(R)) \leq N_m\text{cl}(f(R))$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5) For $R \leq G$, from (4), it follows $f(N_m\text{-}\beta\text{cl}(f^{-1}(R))) \leq N_m\text{cl}(f(f^{-1}(R))) \leq N_m\text{cl}(R)$. Hence we get (5).

(5) \Rightarrow (6) For $S \leq H$, from $N_m\text{int}(S) = Y - N_m\text{cl}(H - S)$ and (5), it follows: $f^{-1}(N_m\text{int}(S)) = f^{-1}(Y - N_m\text{cl}(H - S)) = G - f^{-1}(N_m\text{cl}(H - S)) \leq G - N_m\text{-}\beta\text{cl}(f^{-1}(H - S)) = N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(f^{-1}(S))$. Hence (6) is obtained.

(6) \Rightarrow (1) Let $g \in G$ and O an N_m -open set containing $f(g)$. Then from (6) and Proposition 2.2, it follows $g \in f^{-1}(O) = f^{-1}(N_m\text{int}(O)) \leq N_m\text{-}\beta\text{int}(f^{-1}(O))$. So from Theorem 3.4, we can say that there exists an N_m - β o U containing g such that $g \in U \leq f^{-1}(O)$. Hence f is N_m - β -continuous. □

Theorem 4.3. *Map $f : G \rightarrow H$ be a function on 2 nms (G, N_{mG}) and (H, N_{mH}) . Then the following statements are equivalent:*

1. f is N_m - β -continuous.
2. $f^{-1}(O) \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(f^{-1}(O)))$, for each N_m -open O in H .
3. $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(f^{-1}(F))) \leq f^{-1}(F)$, for each N_m -closed set F in H .
4. $f(N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(R))) \leq N_m \text{cl}(f(R))$, for $R \leq G$.
5. $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(f^{-1}(S))) \leq f^{-1}(N_m \text{cl}(S))$, for $S \leq H$.
6. $f^{-1}(N_m \text{int}(S)) \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(f^{-1}(S)))$, for $S \leq H$.

Proof. (1) \Leftrightarrow (2) It follows from Theorem 4.2 and Definition of N_m - β os.

(1) \Leftrightarrow (3) It follows from Theorem 4.2 and Lemma 3.1.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) Let $R \leq X$. Then from Theorem 4.2(4) and Lemma 3.2, it follows $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(R)) \leq N_m\text{-}\beta \text{cl}(R) \leq f^{-1}(N_m \text{cl}(f(R)))$. Hence $f(N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(R))) \leq N_m \text{cl}(f(R))$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5) Obvious.

(5) \Rightarrow (6) From (5) and Proposition 2.2, it follows: $f^{-1}(N_m \text{int}(S)) = f^{-1}(H - N_m \text{cl}(H - S)) = G - f^{-1}(N_m \text{cl}(H - S)) \leq G - N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(f^{-1}(H - S))) = N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(f^{-1}(S)))$. Hence, (6) is obtained.

(6) \Rightarrow (1) Let O be an N_m -open in H . Then by (6) and Proposition 2.2, we have $f^{-1}(O) = f^{-1}(N_m \text{int}(O)) \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(f^{-1}(O)))$. This implies $f^{-1}(O)$ is an N_m - β o. Hence by (2), f is N_m - β -continuous. \square

Definition 4.2. [10] (G, N_{mG}) be a nms. Then G is said to be N_m - T_2 if for each distinct points g and h of G , there exist two disjoint N_m -open U, V such that $g \in U$ and $h \in V$.

Definition 4.3. (G, N_{mG}) be a nms. Then G is said to be N_m - β - T_2 if for any distinct points g and h of G , there exist disjoint N_m - β o C, D such that $g \in C$ and $h \in D$.

Theorem 4.4. Map $f : G \rightarrow H$ be a map on two nms (G, N_{mG}) and (H, N_{mH}) . If f is an injective and N_m - β continuous map and if H is N_m - T_2 , then G is N_m - β - T_2 .

Proof. Obvious. \square

Theorem 4.5. Map $f : G \rightarrow H$ be a map on two nms (G, N_{mG}) and (H, N_{mH}) . If f is an injective and N_m - β continuous map with an N_m - β -closed graph, then G is N_m - β - T_2 .

Proof. Suppose g_1 and g_2 be any distinct points of G . Then $f(g_1) \neq f(g_2)$, so $(g_1, f(g_2)) \in (G \times H) - L(f)$. Since the graph $L(f)$ is N_m - β c, there exist an N_m - β o containing g_1 and $D \in N_{mH}$ containing $f(g_2)$ such that $f(C) \cap D = \emptyset$. Since f is N_m - β continuous, $f^{-1}(D)$ is an N_m - β o containing g_2 such that $C \cap f^{-1}(D) = \emptyset$. Hence G is N_m - β - T_2 . \square

Definition 4.4. [10] (G, N_{mG}) be a nms and $S \leq G$, S is called N_m -compact (respectively, almost N_m -compact) relative to S if every collection $\{U_i : i \in \Delta\}$ of N_m -open subsets of G such that $S \leq \max \{U_i : i \in \Delta\}$, there exists a finite subset Δ_0 of Δ such that $S \leq \max \{U_j : j \in \Delta_0\}$ (respectively, $S \leq \max \{N_m \text{cl}(U_j) : j \in \Delta_0\}$). (G, N_{mG}) be a nms and $S \leq G$, S is said to be N_m -compact (respectively, almost N_m -compact) if S is N_m -compact (respectively, almost N_m -compact) as a neutrosophic minimal subspace of G .

Definition 4.5. (G, N_mG) be a nms and $S \leq G$, S is called N_m - β -compact (respectively, almost N_m - β -compact) relative to S if every collection $\{U_\delta : \delta \in \Delta\}$ of N_m - β -open subsets of G such that $S \leq \max \{U_\delta : \delta \in \Delta\}$, there exists a finite subset Ω of Δ such that $S \leq \max \{U_\omega : \omega \in \Omega\}$ (respectively, $S \leq \max \{N_m \beta \text{cl}(U_\omega) : \omega \in \Omega\}$). (G, N_mG) be a nms and $S \leq G$, S is said to be N_m - β -compact (respectively, almost N_m - β -compact) if S is N_m - β -compact (resp. almost N_m - β -compact) as a neutrosophic minimal subspace of G .

Theorem 4.6. *Map $f : G \rightarrow H$ be a map on 2 nms (G, N_mG) and (H, N_mH) . If S is an N_m - β -compact set, then $f(S)$ is N_m -compact.*

Proof. Obvious. □

5. N_m -regular open

We introduce following definitions

Definition 5.1. (G, N_mG) be a nms and $A \leq G$, A is called N_m -regular open (in short, N_m -ro) if $A = N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(A))$.

Theorem 5.1. *Any N_m -ro is N_m -open.*

Proof. If A is N_m -ro in (G, N_mG) , $A = N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(A))$. Then $N_m \text{int}(A) = N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(A))) = N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(A)) = A$. That is, A is N_m -open in (G, N_mG) . □

Example 5.1. $G = \{a\}$ with $N_m = \{0_\sim, P, 1_\sim\}$ and $N_m^C = \{1_\sim, Q, 0_\sim\}$ where

$$P = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.5) \succ ; Q = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.5) \succ$$

Now we define the N_m -ro sets as follows:

$$A = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.5) \succ$$

Here $N_m \text{cl}(A) = Q$, $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(A)) = P$ is a N_m -ro in G .

Definition 5.2. (G, N_mG) be a nms and $S \leq G$, S is said to be N_m - π -open set if S is the finite union of N_m -ro.

Remark 5.1. *For a subset of A of an nms (G, N_mG) , we have following implications:*

$$N_m\text{-regular open} \Rightarrow N_m\text{-}\pi\text{-open} \Rightarrow N_m\text{-open}$$

Diagram-I

Example 5.2. $G = \{a\}$ with $N_m = \{0_\sim, P, L, 1_\sim\}$ and $N_m^C = \{1_\sim, M, N, 0_\sim\}$ where

$$P = \prec (0.1, 0.5, 0.1) \succ ; L = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.5) \succ$$

$$M = \prec (0.1, 0.5, 0.1) \succ ; N = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.5) \succ$$

Now we define the two N_m -ro sets as follows:

$$A = \prec (0.1, 0.5, 0.1) \succ$$

$$B = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.5) \succ$$

Here $N_m \text{cl}(A) = M$, $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(A)) = P$; $N_m \text{cl}(B) = N$, $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(B)) = L$ is a N_m -ro set in G . Here, $A \vee B = \prec (0.5, 0.5, 0.1) \succ$ is a N_m - π -open sets but it is not a N_m -ro.

Example 5.3. $G = \{a\}$ with $N_m = \{0_\sim, A, 1_\sim\}$ and $N_m^C = \{1_\sim, B, 0_\sim\}$ where

$A = \prec (0.6, 0.7, 0.3) \succ$; $B = \prec (0.3, 0.3, 0.6) \succ$

Now we define the N_m -ro sets as follows:

$R = \prec (0, 0, 1) \succ$; $S = \prec (1, 1, 0) \succ$

Here $R \vee S = \prec (1, 1, 0) \succ$ is a N_m - π -open set in G . Here, $A = \prec (0.6, 0.7, 0.3) \succ$ is N_m -open but it is not a N_m - π -open.

Conclusion

We presented several definitions, properties, explanations and examples inspired from the concept of N_m - β -open, N_m -regular-open and N_m - π -open. The results of this study may be help in many reserches.

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